

Never Waste a Good Crisis: Did Tax-Avoiding Firms also Record Excessive Profits During the Pandemic?

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Summary

1. Some firms recorded excessive profits during the COVID-19 pandemic. We investigate whether previous tax avoidance practices of these firms relate to their extent of pandemic excess profits.
2. We find a strong correlation between lower effective corporate tax rates and tax haven presence, and excess profits recorded during the pandemic. We argue that this is due to underlying firm preferences for profit-maximization rather than corporate social responsibility or ethical considerations.
3. From a policy perspective, we provide an argument for the fairness of the proposed excess profits tax, since it targets firms that have statistically paid less than their fair share in taxes in the years before the pandemic.
4. Further analysis shows that excess profits were larger in more concentrated industries. This indicates that healthier competition may diminish firms' pricing power and reduce their opportunity to excessively profit off of a crisis.
5. This finding underlines an additional benefit of policies leveling the playing field. To prevent excessive profits during future crises, we recommend policy makers to support small- and medium-sized enterprises, ensuring industries become less concentrated and pricing to become more competitive.

1. Introduction

During the recent COVID-19 pandemic and the energy crisis caused by Russia's invasion of Ukraine, some companies reported record profits. This situation sparked a renewed

policy debate about imposing a windfall or excess profits tax during crises. The media accused businesses of profiteering or 'greedflation,' which means excessively raising prices to benefit from the crises.

Data shows that the share of profits in unit prices increased significantly compared to the share of input costs, giving rise to a discussion about 'sellers' inflation' (Hansen et al., 2023; Weber, 2023). After demand, pricing power was the second largest factor driving profit margins during the pandemic (Skovorodov et al., 2023). According to these authors, "*firms were able to hike final prices, more than compensating for higher costs (...) in a period of decelerating economic activity.*"

These findings suggest that, rather than being purely due to luck or unexpected windfalls, at least part of the excessive profits recorded may have resulted from business decisions with dubious morality or uncompetitive market conditions. The ethics of business decisions leading to excessive profits during times of economic hardship, such as the unprecedented lockdowns and soaring inflation rates of the recent pandemic, have been questioned. Free-market liberals could state that firms were simply maximizing profits, which they argue is their primary or only responsibility (Friedman, 1970). However, from a corporate social responsibility (CSR) perspective, others may argue that firms should not only focus on profits but also attach value to upholding principles that benefit society as a whole (Graafland, 2002; Kolstad, 2007).

Firms may have different views on how to balance profit-maximization with CSR. Differences in these preferences can partly explain variations in excessive profits, even when firms face the same opportunities to hike prices during a pandemic. Additionally, these preferences can influence other socially responsible corporate behavior aspects.

Corporate tax avoidance is another area where firms face a trade-off between maximizing their after-tax profits by exploiting legal grey areas and fulfilling their

moral responsibility to pay their fair share of taxes. This is a significant and growing issue. Nearly 40% of all multinational profits are recorded in tax havens, resulting in a tax revenue loss of 10% worldwide, amounting to hundreds of billions of dollars (Garcia-Bernardo and Janský, 2024; Janský and Palanský, 2019; Tørsløv et al., 2023; Wier and Zucman, 2022).

Research shows that lower CSR is associated with increased tax avoidance (Acosta Garcia et al., 2024; Hoi et al., 2013; Huseynov and Klamm, 2012; Lanis and Richardson, 2015). Since excessive profits may also result from socially undesirable corporate decisions, the extent of these profits during the pandemic may be linked to previous tax-avoiding behavior by the same firms.

In this policy brief, we describe the results and policy implications of our recent research paper on the link between tax avoidance and excess profits recorded during the pandemic (see Further Information, p. 6). The research paper provides empirical evidence for such an association. We also show that industry concentration, as an indicator of lower competition, gave firms the opportunity to record higher excessive profits during the pandemic.

2. Methods

In our research paper, the main methodological challenge in estimating excess profits is defining what 'normal' profits would have been. Traditionally, normal profits were estimated based on the average profits over several previous years (Hebous et al., 2022). However, we use an updated method by Dubinina et al. (2024) that considers a firm's growth rate. Using this method, we calculate excess profits during the pandemic (2020-2021) by comparing them to profits from the six years before the pandemic. We then

analyze how past tax avoidance and industry concentration influenced these excess profits.

The main tax avoidance measures we use as explanatory variables for excess profits are the effective tax rate (ETR) and an indicator signaling whether the business group has an affiliate in a tax haven. The ETR is calculated as taxes paid divided by pre-tax profits. We define tax havens based on the criteria from Dharmapala and Hines (2009) and Hines and Rice (1994). Industry concentration, also used as an explanatory variable of excess profits, is measured by the sales share of the largest firms within a country-industry, classified using the standardized NACE two-digit level. We mainly study the sales share of the top 8 and the top 4 largest firms.

We use the Orbis Historical database from Moody's Analytics to obtain firm financials, ownership data, and industry classifications. This is complemented by yearly industry-level data from Eurostat to observe industry concentration. We control for systematic differences between countries and industries over time using several fixed effects. Additional control variables include firm size, multinational status, and public listing.

3. Tax avoidance, industry concentration and excess profits

In figure 1 in this policy brief, we show the extent of excess profits and total profits for all firms in our sample with positive excess profits. In 2020, total profits for these firms amounted to €1 trillion, while in 2021 this figure grew to €1.75 trillion. In both years, nearly half of these sums were excess profits. This showcases the potential significant tax revenue of an excess profits tax: at a hypothetical tax rate of 10%, the worldwide

revenue of such a tax could already exceed €100 billion.

Note: this figure graphs the sum of excess profits for all firms in our sample with positive excess profits, separately for 2020 and 2021.

The main results of our research paper show a strong link between previous tax avoidance behavior and excess profits recorded during the pandemic. For every percentage point lower effective tax rate (ETR) in preceding years, firms recorded, on average, 0.4% higher excess profits in 2020-2021. Additionally, business groups with affiliates in tax havens recorded 13% higher excess profits than those without such affiliates. These tax avoidance indicators are also strongly correlated with the likelihood of booking positive excess profits.

Furthermore, the ratio of excess profits to total profits is related to tax avoidance. This ratio increases by 0.5 percentage points for every percentage point lower ETR and is 15 percentage points higher for firms with tax haven affiliates.

Our results also indicate that excess profits are higher in more concentrated industries. Firms recorded, on average, 1.5% more excess profits in industries where the sales share of the top 8 or top 4 largest firms was 10 percentage points higher. The interaction estimate of this variable with an indicator for firms in those top 8 or top 4 is statistically not distinguishable from zero, so the estimate of

1.5% is the average for all firms within the more concentrated industry.

4. Conclusions and policy implications

The main finding of our research paper is that firms more likely to have avoided taxes before the coronavirus outbreak also recorded higher excess profits during the pandemic. This empirical evidence supports the idea that these firms have a stronger priority for profits over socially responsible behavior, leading to tax avoidance when possible and to profiteering during the pandemic if given the chance.

This conclusion is highly relevant for policymakers discussing potential excess profits taxation. It supports the implementation of such a tax, as it would primarily target firms that historically have not fully paid their fair share. It also suggests that the tax should be designed to prevent avoidance, as the firms it targets are known to exploit tax loopholes when they can. EU Member States need to harmonize excess profits taxation to avoid regulatory arbitrage and ensure a level playing field.

Our research findings underline the importance of a robust framework against tax avoidance, as it may also prevent other socially undesirable firm behavior. The EU implemented public Country-by-Country Reporting in 2024, obligating large multinationals to provide publicly available information on the amount of profits booked and taxes paid in every country in which they are active. The availability of this information may lead to public pressure, increasing tax compliance. Stronger cooperation between EU tax authorities may also prove beneficial in fighting tax avoidance. Non-EU countries should also consider introducing this public

reporting obligation to ensure worldwide coverage of information on the locations of multinationals' affiliates, profits, and taxes paid. Additionally, Pillar 2, the OECD initiative on a global minimum corporate tax rate that was implemented across over 130 countries in 2024, should decrease tax avoidance. In doing so, it may change firms' preferences regarding pure profit-maximization versus corporate social responsibility, hopefully leading to less excessive profits during future crises.

The additional analysis in the research paper provides evidence for industry concentration leading to larger excess profits. Firms in more concentrated industries recorded higher excess profits. We did not find evidence that this relationship is stronger for the largest firms in more concentrated industries, hence smaller firms in concentrated industries equally excessively profited during the pandemic as larger firms. This conclusion highlights the importance of ensuring fair and healthy competition, so firms do not have the opportunity to use their pricing power to the detriment of consumers during crises.

Policy makers should consider investigations into specific sectors in which anti-competitive practices led to particularly pronounced excess profits during the pandemic. Measures to improve competition in these sectors may include support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to ensure their competitive position against larger firms within their sector and reduce consumers' reliance on these large firms.

Crisis-specific pricing regulations may be activated during public emergencies to prevent price gouging, although it needs to be noted that this may induce hoarding in anticipation of shortages (Chakraborti and Roberts, 2021). Instead of harsh price controls, a monitoring framework may be implemented to track price-setting behavior

and profit margins, to flag potential abuse of crisis situations. Consumer protection law should be strengthened to include the punishment of such abuse and increase transparency in the prices that consumers face.

What is DemoTrans?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Further Information:

Tuinsma, T., De Witte, K., and Titl, V., (2024). Never Waste a Good Crisis: Did Tax-Avoiding Firms also Record Excessive Profits During the Pandemic? Mimeo.

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